

Strengthening Skills for Outbreak Response and Epidemic Modeling in Bucaramanga: Workshop Report

Bucaramanga, Universidad Industrial de Santander

April 27-29, 2023

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Workshop report

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Workshop Course: Theory and Practice of Outbreak Response and Mathematical Modeling of Epidemics

Location: Faculty of Health, Industrial University of Santander, Bucaramanga

Dates: April 27, 28, and 29, 2023

Motivation

The epidemiology of infectious diseases and public health currently require training in analysis, modeling, and decision-making in emergency situations such as epidemics and pandemics. While theoretical training in epidemic theory is necessary to address these challenges, practical training in case studies, execution of plans, and decision-making is equally important.

Activity Description

Two workshops were conducted:

- Workshop 1 (two days): Theory and Practice of Outbreak and Epidemic Response

Prerequisites: None

- Workshop 2 (one day): Mathematical Modeling of Infectious Diseases

Prerequisites: Intermediate to advanced knowledge of R

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Methodology

- Theoretical-practical approach
- Keynote lectures
- Case study practice in groups (Workshop 1)
- Hands-on practice in R (Workshop 2)

Participant Profile

- For **Workshop 1 (two days): Theory and Practice of Outbreak and Epidemic Response**
Target audience: Final-year medical and nursing students from the Industrial University of Santander.
Prerequisites: None
- For **Workshop 2 (one day): Mathematical Modeling of Infectious Diseases**
Target audience: Master's students from the Industrial University of Santander.
Prerequisites: Intermediate knowledge of R

Capacity

Each workshop had a maximum capacity of 30 participants.

Team

- **Zulma M. Cucunubá:** Principal Investigator (Pontificia Universidad Javeriana).
- **Laura Gómez Bermeo:** Training Coordinator (Pontificia Universidad Javeriana).
- **Miguel Gamez:** Software Team (Pontificia Universidad Javeriana).

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Agenda

Day 1 - Thursday, April 27, 2023

Activity	Objective	Description
<p>Epidemic Theory Lecture</p> <p>Duration: 1 hour</p>	<p>Introduce key concepts of epidemic theory</p>	<p>This lecture provided an introduction to epidemic theory, exploring fundamental concepts in infectious disease epidemiology. A brief history of major epidemics and pandemics was covered, emphasizing their impact on society and the evolution of prevention and control strategies.</p>
<p>Epidemic Theory Workshop (Zika Part A)</p> <p>Duration: 2 hours</p>	<p>Learn basic concepts of infectious disease modeling using diagrams and mathematical formulas with a simple Zika infection model.</p>	<p>In this hands-on workshop, participants learned basic concepts of infectious disease modeling using pen and paper. Through diagrams and simple mathematical formulas, they explored a basic model of Zika infection. Attendees were guided in constructing a diagram and using equations to describe how the infected population changed over time.</p>
<p>Step-by-Step Guide to Outbreak Investigation Lecture</p> <p>Duration: 2 hours</p>	<p>Explore participant expectations, experiences, and challenges in working with public health data.</p>	<p>This session aimed to address the cleaning and organization of epidemiological data using RStudio.</p>

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Day 2 - Friday, April 28, 2023

Activity	Objective	Description
<p>Talk on the "Outbreak Guide Review"</p> <p>Duration: 1 hour</p>	<p>Apply the concepts, definitions, and theoretical aspects of outbreak investigation to articles on five major outbreaks.</p>	<p>In this talk, a series of recommendations were presented for reviewing definitions such as R_0, R_t, incubation period, and other terms related to outbreaks.</p>
<p>Workshop (Part A): Outbreak Study and Application of the Outbreak Study Guide</p> <p>Duration: 3 hours</p>	<p>Recognize key elements and fundamental strategies of risk communication for public health.</p>	<p>Through group work, a hands-on outbreak workshop was conducted, studying cases of Measles, Nipah, Venezuelan Equine Encephalitis, and Cholera to analyze epidemics using the parameters, concepts, and definitions provided in the theoretical component.</p>
<p>Workshop (Part B): Presentation of Results (by Groups), Discussion, and Group Feedback.</p> <p>Duration: 3 hours</p>	<p>Facilitate the presentation of results by each group, encouraging collaborative feedback to improve analysis and decision-making in outbreak management.</p>	<p>In this activity, each group presented the results of their simulated outbreak analysis, detailing the strategies they developed to investigate and control the disease. After each presentation, a discussion space was opened, allowing other groups to ask questions, share observations, and provide constructive feedback. This collaborative dynamic enabled participants to reflect on their approaches, identify improvements, and learn from the experiences and perspectives of other teams, enhancing their ability to make decisions in real outbreak management situations.</p>

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Day 3 - Friday, April 29, 2023

Activity	Objective	Description
<p>Lecture: “Epidemic Theory”</p> <p>Duration: 1 hour</p>	<p>To introduce key concepts of epidemic theory.</p>	<p>This talk provided an introduction to epidemic theory, exploring fundamental concepts in the epidemiology of infectious diseases. A brief history of the most significant epidemics and pandemics was discussed, highlighting their impact on society and the evolution of prevention and control strategies.</p>
<p>Workshop: Epidemic Theory (Zika Part A)</p> <p>Duration: 2 hours</p>	<p>Learn basic concepts of infectious disease modeling through the use of diagrams and mathematical formulas, using a basic model of Zika infection.</p>	<p>In this hands-on workshop, participants learned basic concepts of infectious disease modeling using pen and paper. Through diagrams and simple mathematical formulas, they explored a basic model of Zika infection. Attendees were guided in constructing a diagram and using equations to describe how the infected population changed over time.</p>
<p>Workshop: Epidemic Theory (Zika Part B)</p> <p>Duration: 2 hours</p>	<p>Use R for modeling a basic Zika infection model.</p>	<p>In this hands-on workshop, the diagram and equations were translated to describe how the infected population changed over time using the R programming language.</p>

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Initial Characterization

A total of 48 participants attended:

- 38% undergraduate in Medicine.
- 31% undergraduate in Nursing.
- 10% Master's in Epidemiology.
- 17% Others.
- 80% of the attendees were students.
- 6 out of 10 participants were between 18 and 24 years old.
- 60% of the participants were women.

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Development and Evaluation of activities

Day 1 - Thursday, April 27, 2023

Activity	Comments	Results
<p>Lecture on "Epidemic Theory"</p> <p>Duration: 1 hour</p>	<p>During the session, there was active and dynamic participation from the students.</p>	<p>The historical context serves as a motivating factor in the learning process. However, it is important to include female references and professionals from fields such as nursing.</p> <p>The topic of epidemic theory generates interest, curiosity, and a better understanding of models among students. Presenting key concepts at the beginning is crucial to ensure that all participants have a solid theoretical foundation and a common understanding of the subject.</p>
<p>Workshop on Epidemic Theory (Zika - Part A)</p> <p>Duration: 2 hours</p>	<p>Collaboration between nursing and medical students provided valuable complementarity, considering the conceptual understanding required for each discipline, despite being initially challenging for students.</p>	<p>When introducing the vector model, students expressed significant doubts about understanding the model and equations, as the theoretical context had been primarily human-centered.</p>
<p>Lecture: Step-by-Step Outbreak Investigation</p> <p>Duration: 2 hours</p>	<p>During the session, there was active and dynamic participation from the students.</p>	<p>Presenting the steps of the investigation, expected analyses, and anticipated outcomes is essential for clarity and effective learning.</p>

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Day 2 - Friday, April 28, 2023

Activity	Comments	Results
<p>Lecture on "Outbreak Study Guide Review"</p> <p>Duration: 1 hour</p>	<p>During the session, there was active and dynamic participation from the students.</p>	<p>Theoretical concepts are crucial for understanding and critically analyzing articles. Students developed reasoning and analytical skills regarding epidemics by understanding parameters such as R_0, R_t, etc.</p>
<p>Workshop (Part A) Outbreak Study and Application of the Outbreak Study Guide</p> <p>Duration: 3 hours</p>	<p>Students were able to understand the sociocultural, economic, and religious context, as well as the collection and analysis of epidemiological parameters, epidemic curve analysis, and other aspects that define the epidemic's characteristics for decision-making. Some difficulties arose in understanding and applying epidemiological parameters.</p>	<p>The groups successfully analyzed epidemics through their contextual factors, which contributed to their interest and motivation in the training topics. This helped them contextualize and grasp the significance of the epidemics studied.</p>
<p>Workshop (Part B) Presentation of Results (by Groups), Socialization, and Group Feedback</p> <p>Duration: 3 hours</p>	<p>Students delivered their presentations within a maximum of 10 minutes, using key community communication strategies such as TikTok, infographics, storytelling, among others</p>	<p>The most commonly used communication strategies involved digital media with short attention spans and real-life simulation scenarios. By understanding the course of epidemics and their characteristics, students were able to make deductions regarding aspects such as pandemic potential and public health risks.</p>

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Day 3 - Friday, April 29, 2023

Activity	Comments	Results
<p>Conference: "Epidemic Theory"</p> <p>Duration: 1 hour</p>	<p>Students actively participated in the session. Introducing key concepts at the beginning ensures a solid theoretical foundation and common understanding, especially for master's students from different fields.</p>	<p>Participants gained a better understanding of epidemic theory, reinforcing their analytical skills.</p>
<p>Workshop on Epidemic Theory (Zika Part A)</p> <p>Duration 2 hours</p>	<p>Students successfully followed the step-by-step guide.</p>	<p>The workshop was completed within the scheduled time, using pre-validated materials.</p>
<p>Workshop on Epidemic Theory (Zika Part B)</p> <p>Duration: 2 hours</p>	<p>Students successfully introduced the model in R and discussed possible outcomes.</p>	<p>The workshop was completed within the scheduled time, using pre-validated materials.</p>

Workshop course evaluation

Evaluation Results Group 1

- 19 participants (54% of total attendees) completed the survey, with 68% being nursing students.
- 100% of respondents stated that the workshop provided useful theoretical and practical knowledge for their professional development.
- The overall course rating was 4.5.

Some comments on **what participants liked the most:**

"The application as doctors, strategies to face future epidemics."

"The theoretical and practical management of the proposals throughout the workshop."

"What I liked the most was the theoretical component, where thanks to the speaker, the main aspects of epidemiology were widely understood. Additionally, the speaker's expertise and passion for the topic motivate further inquiry and deeper exploration in this field."

"The willingness to answer questions."

"Interdisciplinarity."

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"The outbreak investigation guide workshop, the dynamic was good."

Some comments on **what participants found most challenging** were:

"Meeting new people."

"For those who did not study epidemiology in their degree programs, it was a lot of information in a short amount of time to fully understand."

"The need to integrate mathematical concepts."

"The theoretical part is too short and should place more emphasis on prior or basic knowledge. From the nursing program perspective, I see that the focus is on health; however, the content is much more oriented toward medicine rather than nursing in conceptual terms."

"The mathematical formulas used in outbreak management."

Some comments on **areas for improvement** were:

- Sending materials before the session.
- Improving the timing and scheduling of the workshops.
- "Perhaps conducting a practical SIR exercise, meaning with actual data."
- Continuing to strengthen these types of activities.

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Some **suggestions**:

- Allocate more time for explaining the equations.
- Extend the duration of the second workshop.
- "Ensure the workshop is designed for a broader audience, not just those with medical training."

Evaluation Results Group 2

4.9.

- Survey response rate: 70%.
- Most participants reported having a basic level of R, rather than intermediate or advanced.
- 100% of respondents stated that the workshop provided useful theoretical and practical knowledge for their professional development.
- The overall workshop rating was

Participant Feedback on Activities – Group 2

"The conference session was quite dense in content and terminology. Consider alternating with practical activities and possibly using a simulation to support the explanation."

"Excellent initiative, human resources, and materials."

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“A very well-developed workshop, understandable even for professionals who are not directly in this field of study.”

“I found the methodology in both the lectures and workshops excellent—very didactic and conducive to learning. Congratulations, excellent work.”

“Thank you for allowing us not only to learn but also to advance professionally. The R module was very helpful and provided a new perspective on the tool, making it more didactic. Many thanks for the workshop.”

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Conclusions and Recommendations

- Provide materials in advance for participants to review before the training.
- Reassess the schedule and duration of sessions.
- The Zika Part A material can be successfully completed by undergraduate students. Zika Part B, which requires R, was not tested with them.

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- Adjustments made to the outbreak investigation guide improved the overall experience.
- The creation of materials for community outreach was a motivating exercise that encouraged creativity and civic engagement.
- Consider evaluating individual activities.

Questions and Reflections

- What possible biases are we incorporating in the design of content and materials? What about the hidden curriculum?
- How can we include and engage diverse audiences within heterogeneous groups?
- What are the different learning pathways based on participants' profiles? How can these be integrated into a virtual environment?